

hot and acetone was removed, when a pale brown product was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol. The mixed m.p. with 7-*n*-butoxy flavone obtained by oxidation of the chalcone by selenium dioxide was not lowered.

7-*n*-Butoxy flavonol: The chalcone (0.5 g) was mixed with NaOH (15 ml, 10%) and then methanol (15 ml) was added. The mixture was warmed, if necessary to obtain a clear solution. It was cooled in ice, H₂O₂ (4 ml., 17%) was added and left in ice-bath for 2 hr and then overnight at room temperature. It turned greenish yellow. It was then poured into ice-water and acidified. The substance was collected and crystallised from ethanol. It develops a greenish fluorescence with conc. H₂SO₄. The flavonols thus obtained are recorded in Table 2.

7-*n*-Butoxy flavanones: 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxy-chalcone (0.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with sulphuric acid (20 ml; 10%) when turbidity appeared. It was dissolved by adding more ethanol (10 ml) and the solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 24 hr. Ethanol was then distilled off and the residual solution was filtered hot and left at room temperature when flavanone was obtained. It was crystallised from petrol-ether colourless crystals. The results are summarised in Table 3.

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Spectrophotometric and Conductometric study of Chelates of Divalent Calcium and Divalent Zinc with 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Lawsonie)

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SURVEY of literature reveals that 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (Lawsonie) has found its application in qualitative and quantitative estimations of various metals¹⁻⁴. Recently we have reported the chelate of Lawsonie with lanthanum⁵ spectrophotometrically and conductometrically.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Lawsonie (K.K. Laboratories I.N.C. Plainview, New York, A.R.) and Calcium

nitrate and Zinc nitrate of B.D.H. AnalaR grade were prepared by dissolving the respective compound in double distilled ethyl alcohol (absolute).

To isolate the complexes, 200 ml of Lawsonie (alcoholic) solution (0.01M) was added slowly to the beaker containing 200 ml of metal ions (0.01M) with constant stirring. After addition the solution was warmed and allowed to stand overnight. The yellowishred (Ca-lawsonie complex) and pomegranate red (Zn-Lawsonie complex) coloured crystals appeared, were filtered, and washed several times with ice-cold water and dried at 70°-75° and 62°-68° respectively.

The isolated complexes were analysed for metal content gravimetrically.

Baush and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements, Perkin-Elmer infra red spectrophotometer for infra-red spectra, were used.

Results and Discussion

It has been observed that the order of addition of reactants had no appreciable effect on absorbance.

Nature of chelates

To find the nature of chelates formed and working wave length Garg, Singh and Kotyal⁶ method was used. For this, mixtures containing equal proportions of metal ions and lawsonie were mixed and the absorbance measured. The absorption maximum of the complex were found to be at 475 nm and 465 nm respectively.

Composition of the chelates

The composition of the chelates were established by the method of Job's continuous variation⁷, molar ratio⁸, slope ratio⁹ and Dey¹⁰. A large number of observations were taken at 475 nm and 465 nm and it was found that the ratio of Ca⁺⁺ Lawsonie and Zn⁺⁺ : Lawsonie is 1 : 1 in each case.

Molecular Formula of the Chelate

Chemical analysis of Ca-Lawsonie chelate

From analysis it was found that amount of calcium, C and H are 10.7%, 45.6% and 4.7% and calculated values are 10.9%, 45.7% and 4.6% respectively which correspond to the formula [(C₁₀H₅O₃)(Ca)(C₂H₅OH)₂]⁺NO₃⁻.

The fact that nitrate is not in coordination sphere was further confirmed by conductance shown by chelate in alcoholic solution.

Chemical analysis of Zn-Lawsonie chelate

In Zn-Lawsonie chelate the % of Zn, C and H are 16.2%, 42.6% and 4.4% and the calculated values are 16.5%, 42.8% and 4.3% respectively which correspond to the formula

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The fact that nitrate is not in co-ordination sphere was further confirmed by the conductance shown by chelate in alcoholic solution.

Hence the molecular formula of Ca-Lawsone chelate and Zn-Lawsone chelate are $[(C_{10}H_5O_3)(Ca)(C_2H_5OH)_2]^+NO_3^-$ and $[(C_{10}H_5O_3)(Zn)(C_2H_5OH)_2]^+NO_3^-$ respectively.

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Application of Thermographic Analysis in the Studies of Reclaimed Rubber Compounds Effect of Accelerators and Antioxidant

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EARLIER reports illustrated the effects of (i) replacement of natural rubber by reclaim in a compound¹, (ii) increment of the preparation of sulphur in an accelerated reclaim mix² and (iii) stearic

acid and zinc oxide in accelerated high-as well as low-sulphur reclaim compound². The effects of (a) changing the type of accelerator in high- and low-sulphur reclaim compounds and (b) an antioxidant on a representative reclaim compound as well as on the reclaim are the subjects of this communication.

Effect of Accelerators

The recipe of these high- and low-sulphur compounds are shown in Table I, their DTA thermograms being shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively, Curves A, B, C, D, E (Figure 1) and a, b, c, d, e (Figure 2) represent respectively the high- and low-sulphur compounds using different types of accelerators.

In the case of high-sulphur compounds Tm of sulphur (monoclinic) around 110°-120° has been exhibited more or less prominently in different accelerator systems, accompanied, in some cases, by the Tm of stearic acid and zinc stearate as has been observed previously². Similar observations have been noted in low-sulphur compounds. The primary exotherm appears to be principally due to the curing in the case of high-sulphur systems, but the profiles of the curves for different systems containing different accelerators exhibit their own characteristics quite clearly. Peak height in case of high-sulphur compounds remains practically unchanged, although this parameter gradually increases in the order DPG < MBT < CBS < TMTD < BA in low-sulphur compounds. The height of increase of high-sulphur compounds (that are almost identical irrespective of the type of accelerator used) lies approximately intermediate between the maximum and minimum value of peak height in the low-sulphur compounds. Fractional peak area as used²⁻⁴ and stated² earlier, in case of high-sulphur compound are almost the same in case of BA and TMTD accelerator systems (curves A and E) whereas in the remaining systems like DPG, MBT and CBS (curves B, C, D) this area is of comparable magnitude, but somewhat different from that of the previous two

TABLE I—FORMULATION OF HIGH- AND LOW-SULPHUR COMPOUNDS** ANALYSED BY DTA

	High-sulphur					Low-sulphur				
	A	B	C	D	E	a	b	c	d	e
Reclaim	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Stearic acid	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Zinc oxide	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
BA††	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—
DPG†	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—
MBT*	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—
CBS‡	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—
TMTD‡‡	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5
Sulphur	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5

** Formulation are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim

†† Butyraldehyde aniline

† Diphenylguanidine

* 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole

‡ N-cyclohexyl benzothiazole-2-sulphonamide

‡‡ Tetramethylthiuram disulphide.